

OPEN PROBLEMS IN NUMERICAL DESCRIPTION AND OPTIMAL DESIGN OF COMPOSITE THERMOFORMING PROCESS

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INTRODUCTION

Now, fiber reinforced polymeric materials are widely used in various branches of modern industry – see Fig.1. However, a high volume (mass) production of composite structures requires the detailed analysis, design and optimization of the technological process both from the quality of the final product point of view and additionally taking in to account the total cost of the production.

To model and then optimize a production process of continuous fibre reinforced structures with high performance properties and a complex geometry it is necessary to satisfy a series of conditions dealing with the following groups of problems:

- Numerical modelling of the process with the use of FEM (finite element method) versus CVM (control volume method),
- Description of heating of a resin, consolidation of a laminate and of cooling stages for thermosetting and thermoplastic resins,
- The influence of thermal process (heating and cooling) on wrinkling and fibre buckling, on the change of fibre orientations by thermal or chemical deformation and on the residual stresses,
- Optimization of the thermoforming process by controlling process conditions being design variables of optimization problem.

Fig.1 Composite plates made with the use of thermoforming process

GOVERNING RELATIONS

For the non-isothermal thermoforming process the fundamental set of equations should describe simultaneously different stages of the technological process, i.e.: (1) the behaviour of the fluid (the synthetic resin) during the filling of the mould coupled with (2) a heat transfer analysis from the mould walls and (3) the reactive nature and complex rheology of reactive materials (the viscosity and curing kinetics) during the gelation stage of the process. The Navier-Stokes equations are commonly used in modelling of a such class of problems, however, they are supplemented by a set of additional relations describing the viscosity and curing kinetics. In the case of the viscous Newtonian fluid the set of fundamental Navier-Stokes equations may be written in the following integral form:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \int_{\Omega} \bar{W} d\Omega + \oint_{\partial\Omega} (\bar{F}_c - \bar{F}_v) dS = \int_{\Omega} \bar{Q} d\Omega \quad (1)$$

or in the equivalent differential form:

$$\frac{\partial \bar{W}}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\bar{F}_c - \bar{F}_v) = \bar{Q} \quad (2)$$

where:

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{W}^{Tr} &= [\rho, \rho V_j, \rho E], & \bar{F}_c^{Tr} &= [\rho V, \rho V_i V_j + p \delta_{ij}, \rho H V], & \bar{F}_v^{Tr} &= [0, \tau_{ij}, \Theta_i] \\ \bar{Q}^{Tr} &= [0, \rho f_i, \rho f_i V_i + \dot{q}_h], & \Theta_i &= V_j \tau_{ij} + \lambda \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_i}, & H &= h + \frac{1}{2} V_i V_i = E + \frac{p}{\rho}, & h &= cT \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

The above relations describe the exchange (flux) of mass, momentum and energy through the boundary $\partial\Omega$ of a control volume Ω , which is fixed in space. There are two flux vectors \bar{F}_c, \bar{F}_v . The first one is related to the convective transport of the quantities in the fluid. Usually it is termed vector of convective fluxes, although for the momentum and the energy equation it also includes the pressure terms $p \bar{n}$ where p denotes a static pressure and \bar{n} is a unit, normal vector. \bar{V} means the velocity vector having the components V_j . The second flux vector – vector of viscous fluxes, contains the viscous stresses τ_{ij} defined in the following way:

$$\tau_{ij} = \mu \left(\frac{V_i}{x_j} + \frac{V_j}{x_i} \right) - \frac{2}{3} \mu \frac{\partial V_l}{\partial x_l} \delta_{ij} \quad (4)$$

as well as the heat diffusion, where T is a temperature, λ is a thermal conductivity coefficient and μ - molecular fluid viscosity coefficient. H is the total enthalpy, h means the enthalpy and f_i are components of the body forces whereas \dot{q}_h denotes the time rate of the heat transfer per a unit mass. E denotes the total energy of a fluid per a unit mass.

The above general relations describing flow of the resin and the heat transfer have to be supplemented by the equations characterizing the rheokinetics of the resin in the sense of the viscosity relations:

$$\eta = \frac{\mu}{\rho} = B \exp\left(\frac{T_b}{T}\right) \cdot \left(\frac{\alpha_g}{\alpha_g - \alpha}\right)^{C_1 + C_2 \cdot \alpha} \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = \dot{q}_h = (k_1 + k_2\alpha^m) \cdot (1-\alpha)^n, \quad k_i = A_i e^{\frac{-E_i}{RT}}, \quad i=1,2 \quad (6)$$

where : B, C_1, C_2, T_b – constants; T – the absolute temperature.; $\alpha_g = 0.65$ (65% of a cured material); α - degree of cure at the given temperature T , [%]; m, n - constants; k_i - reaction rate constants; A_i - pre-exponential factors; E_i - activation energies; R - the universal gas constant. According to this model a degree of cure at time t is defined as: $\alpha = \frac{G(t)}{G_\Sigma}$ where $G(t)$ - the heat of reaction released at time t at a given temperature, and G_Σ - the total heat of reaction at a sufficiently high temperature at which the resin is perfectly cured. Dependy on the used model the coefficient k_1 may be identically equal to zero (the model Bogetti, Gillespie) [1] or not. The infiltration of the viscous resin through a porous medium (fibers) is characterised by the 3-D Darcy flow rule in the following form:

$$V_i = \frac{\mathbf{K}}{\eta} (\nabla p)_i \quad (7)$$

The set of equations (1)-(7) is supplemented by the boundary and initial conditions formulated at the resin inlet, at the boundaries of the mould and at the free surface of the resin filling the mould.

SIMPLIFICATION OF THE MODEL

The permeability tensor

In general, the permeability tensor \mathbf{K} in the Darcy flow rule (7) has nine independent components. Our analysis is especially devoted to the 1-D problems and if one considers the vertical position of the mould and assumes a horizontal resin front, which is constant over the preform's thickness, the infiltration kinetics can be written one-dimensional as:

$$V = -\frac{1}{\eta} \frac{k}{L} \Delta p \quad (8)$$

where L is the length of the preform and the permeability tensor \mathbf{K} has one component only denoted by k – the permeability in the direction of infiltration. The macroscopic flow in the mould is governed mainly by the geometry of the fibre architecture, i.e. by the fibre volume content Φ and the fibre radius r . The permeability k can then be expressed by the formulation of Carman and Kozeny [1,2]:

$$k = \frac{r^2}{4K_z} \frac{(1-\Phi)^3}{\Phi^2} \quad (9)$$

with K_z as the Kozeny constant. This equation indicates for example that for fibre contents of 100 % or for infinitively small fibres, respectively, the permeability leads theoretically to zero. Vice versa, the infiltration velocity increases with thicker fibres and lower fibre volume contents. To validate the theory, a number of tests have been conducted. In several pre-tests the permeability constant k has been determined experimentally for carbon fabrics. With HTA plain woven fabrics of 61 % fibre content, k amounts to $1.63 \cdot 10^{-11} \text{ m}^2$, corresponding to a Kozeny constant K_z of $K_z = 0.03$; $r = 0.7 \text{ mm}$, $\Phi = 0.4$

With these results, an estimation of a suitable RTM cycle in terms of pressure difference Δp and the infiltration time t for a complete preform impregnation can be conducted. By transformation of eqn (8) one obtains the equation for the pressure difference between the two ends of the preform

$$\Delta p = \frac{L^2 \eta}{2kt} \quad (10)$$

Rheokinetics of the resin

The degree of cure α is a function of time t and a temperature T . However, assuming that in the time interval $[t_1, t_2]$ the temperature T is constant the relation (6) can be simplified since k_1 and k_2 parameters are constants and the relation (6) can be integrated analytically. If k_2 is equal to zero the variations of the degree of cure can be expressed as follows:

$$\alpha(t) = 1 - [k_1(n-1)t + 1]^{-\frac{1}{n-1}}, T(t) = \text{const} \quad (11)$$

In this case the distribution of the degree of cure takes the form presented in Fig.2.

Fig.2. Distributions of the degree of cure with time ($T(t)=\text{const}$)

In addition, as the temperature distribution is a known in advance function of time the equation (6) can be also integrated using simple procedures.

MODELLING OF THE LAMINATE NON-MECHANICAL STRAINS

The non-mechanical strains induced into fibres during the process cycle are composed of two parts: (1) chemical strains, (2) thermal strains. Both of them results in the arising of residual stresses in the product and may be high enough to cause matrix cracking or fibres debonding even before mechanical loading (Donner, Novak [3]). Finally, it may result in the significant decrease of static (fatigue) strength and on the other hand a possible microcracking exposes fibres to chemical degradation. In modelling of the above process it is assumed that the chemical strains may be induced in the transverse direction to the fibres and are expressed as follows:

$$e_2^c = \beta_1 + \beta_2 10^{\beta_3 \alpha} \quad \alpha \leq \alpha^c \quad (12)$$

$$e_2^c = e_2^{cf} \quad \alpha > \alpha^c$$

where: e^c the laminate chemical strains, β_1 , β_2 and β_3 are empirical coefficients, α^c is the degree of cure when chemical shrinkage is completed and e_2^{cf} is the final chemical shrinkage strain. The thermal strains induced in the fibres are defined in a classical way:

$$e_i^T = \gamma_i \cdot (T - T_0) \quad (13)$$

where γ_1 is a thermal expansion coefficient and T_0 is the initial stress free temperature. The transverse modulus dependence on degree of cure α is modeled by the expressions:

$$\bar{E}_{2i}(\alpha) = E \quad \alpha < \alpha^* \quad (14)$$

$$\bar{E}_{2i}(\alpha) = a_0 + a_1\alpha + a_2\alpha^2 \quad \alpha^* \leq \alpha$$

$$\bar{E}_1(\alpha) = \bar{E}_{11i} + (\bar{E}_{1f} - \bar{E}_{1i}) \cdot \alpha \quad (15)$$

$$\bar{\nu}_{12}(\alpha) = \bar{\nu}_{12i} + (\bar{\nu}_{12f} - \bar{\nu}_{12i}) \cdot \alpha \quad (16)$$

The mechanical properties are used to determine the time-dependent stiffnesses, and in this way one may evaluate the induced during the RTM process time-dependent moment resultants arising in the laminate:

$$M_1(t) = -M_2(t) = h^2 \int_0^t d\tau F\{\alpha(t), [\xi(t) - \xi(\tau)]\} [e_1(\tau) - e_2(\tau)] \quad (17)$$

where:

$$F(\alpha, t) = \frac{Q_{12}^2(\alpha, t) + Q_{11}(\alpha, t) \cdot Q_{22}(\alpha, t)}{Q_{11}(\alpha, t) + Q_{22}(\alpha, t) + 2Q_{12}(\alpha, t)}, \quad \xi(x) = \int_0^x \frac{ds}{a_T[T(s)]}, \quad a_T(T) = \exp\left(\frac{B_1}{T} - B_2\right)$$

The described above model has been introduced by White and Hahn [4]. It should be mentioned that it has a lot of simplifications due to the assumptions, however, it allows to obtain some pieces of information dealing with the process.

OPTIMIZATION PROBLEM

In thermoforming processes both chemical reactions, fibers deformations and resin shrinkage are controlled by two sets of parameters: 1) temperature of each of the external electric heaters located inside the mould and 2) the time interval of the heating, consolidation and cooling stages of the process taking also into account the time periods corresponding to the increase or decrease of temperatures between different phases of the process – see Fig.3. The mentioned above two sets of parameters are treated as design variables in the optimization problem. In general, they constitute a set of ten variables corresponding to coordinates of five points plotted in Fig.3, i.e.:

$$\{(t_1, T_1), (t_2, T_2), (t_3, T_3), (t_4, T_4), (t_5, T_5)\} \quad (18)$$

However, only six of them is independent and finallym they constitute the chromosome used in the optimisation analysis. In addition, all (i.e. six) of continuous are discretised in order to represent them in a binary form convenient for further use in the optimisation procedures.

Fig.3 Thermal characteristics of the thrmforming process

The quality of the final product understood in the sense of the resin/fibres shrinkage and fiber deformation is analysed mainly in the sense of the values of residual stresses existing in composite structures at the end of the thermoforming technological process. They are treated as a measure of the process effectiveness. Therefore the optimization problem is formulated in the following way:

$$MinMax \quad \sigma_{res}(s) \tag{19}$$

where s denotes the set of design variables mentioned above, and the value of residual stresses is evaluated with the help of eqn (17).

Fig.4. A schematic view of the RTM process

Numerical analysis have been conducted for plated structures made of unidirectional carbon fibres/resin – see Fig.4. Genetic algorithms have been used herein to find the optimal solutions. The analysis shows the differences in the distributions of residual stresses for thermoplastic and

thermosetting resin in the case of the constant temperature distribution around the mould and for the standard heating/cooling regime. It leads finally to different results of optimal thermoforming process. The results are discussed in view of different rather phenomenological laws characterizing the origin of residual stresses in fibres for both types of resins.

REMARKS ON NUMERICAL MODELING

Taking into account thick composite elements produced with the use of thermoforming process it is necessary to study the filling process and distributions of temperatures and of degree of cure with time in order to model correctly the optimisation problem. The simple numerical example demonstrated in Fig.5 shows evidently the necessity of numerical analysis. In the model a source of internal heating is placed inside the wall to examine the effects of chemical reactions occurring during the gelation of the resin. In addition, the example exhibit a good correlation between the results obtained with the use of finite elements and finite volume procedures.

Fig.5. The heat transfer through the plate wall – the accuracy of numerical modeling

Many different methodologies were devised to conduct spatial discretisation of the Navier-Stokes equations, i.e. the numerical approximation of the convective and viscous fluxes and of the source term. In order to classify and sort them we can divide the spatial discretisation schemes into the following three main categories: (1) finite difference (FD), (2) finite element (FE) and (3) finite volume (FV). All schemes rely on some kind of grid in order to discretise the governing relations (1) – (7). Commonly two types of grids exist: (1) structured grids – each grid point is uniquely identified by the indices and the corresponding Cartesian coordinates; the grid cells are quadrilaterals in 2-D formulation and hexahedra in 3-D; the grid may be also curvilinear for so-called body-fitted grids and (2) unstructured grids – grid cells and grid points have no particular ordering; they usually consist of a mix of quadrilaterals and triangles in 2-D and of hexahedra, tetrahedra, prisms and pyramids in 3-D in order to resolve the boundary layers properly – they are called also as hybrid or mix grids.

The finite element method was originally employed for structural analysis only. However, at the beginning of 90's, did the FE method gain the popularity in the solution of the flow problems. The FE method is attractive because of its integral formulation and the use of unstructured grids, which are both preferable for flows in or around complex geometries. This method is also particularly suitable for treatment of non-Newtonian fluids. The FE method has a very rigorous mathematical foundation. Although it can be shown in certain cases that the method is mathematically equivalent to the FV discretisation, the numerical effort is much higher. This may explain why the FV method became more popular. Sometimes both methods are combined – particularly on unstructured grids. In both FD and FE techniques the calculation of grids (meshes) change at every time step.

In order to circumvent the above-mentioned problem with the mesh regeneration the FV method is widely used. The FV method directly utilises the conservation laws – the integral formulation of the Navier-Stokes equations – eqn (1). The main advantage of the FV method is that the spatial discretisation is carried out directly in the physical space. Thus, there are no problems with any transformation between coordinate system. It can be easily implemented on structured as well as on unstructured grids. The FV method is based on the direct discretisation of the conservation laws, the laws are also conserved by the numerical scheme. Therefore, the FV method has an ability to compute weak solutions of the governing equations correctly. Under certain conditions the FV method is equivalent to the FD method or to a low-order FE method.

The discussed above methods deal with the spatial discretisation only since majority of numerical schemes used in the solution of the Navier-Stokes equations apply to the method where a separate discretisation in space and in time (so-called the method of lines) is introduced. Therefore, to supplement the above review it is necessary to mention that, in general, two different discretisations in time schemes are employed herein, i.e. explicit and implicit temporal discretisation. A broader discussion of those schemes can be found e.g. in the monograph [5].

We do not intend to dwell herein on different variants of numerical methods applied in the fluid dynamics problems. However, the presented here brief classification of the used approaches should help in understanding of our choice of the numerical package applied in view of a numerical simulation of the RIM technological process and of further optimisation procedures.

With regard to optimisation problems dealing with the numerical analysis of the Navier-Stokes equations for technological processes one may distinguish two general groups of objectives:

- Shape optimisation of moulds (or dies) resembling structural shape optimisation problems and in view of that FE packages are rather preferred since the numerical formulation of a such class of problems is well established,
- Optimisation of parameters or/and boundary and initial conditions of technological processes and in such an analysis the advantages in the application of the FV method are rather obvious taking also into account the presented above discussion of used numerical methods.

However, it is also obvious that the FV packages used in the numerical simulation and optimisation should satisfy additional conditions enabling us to model and optimise the discussed problem in a correct manner, especially taking into account the following factors:

- modelling of both 3-D and 2-D fluid flow, heat and mass transfer problems,
- description of a wide range of chemical reactions and related phenomena,
- computational effectiveness in the sense of optimisation and reduction of computational time required in the analysis,
- interface to external CAD systems in order to mesh easily real, complex engineering structures,
- flexibility in cooperation with external optimisation procedures what in our opinion is especially supported by the use of the C language and possibility of defining user's own subroutines and procedures.

NUMERICAL RESULTS

In order to demonstrate the effectiveness and necessity of the optimisation analysis in thermoforming process the optimisation problem (18), (19) has been solved for rectangular plates made of carbon/epoxy resin (see Figs 1 and 4) made of cross ply laminates [0,90]_s.

Three different optimisation problems have been formulated and solved:

- analytical analysis taking into account simplifications of relations mentioned in section 3 and assuming constant temperature distributions in all directions of the plate during the cooling stage
 - two separate cases have been examined:
 - $k_1=0$ in eqn (6)
 - $k_1>0$ in eqn (6)
- numerical analysis – the full set of equations (1)–(7) have been solved using finite volume package

Variations of maximal residual stresses for all cases considered herein are presented in Fig. 6. As it may be observed there is a significant difference in the values of residual stresses for different variants of the analysis, i.e. $k_1=0$ and $k_1>0$.

Fig.6 Maximal residual stresses

However, the differences between numerical and analytical studies are almost negligible. In addition, for both cases the form of the optimal chromosome (see eqn (18) and Fig.3) is almost the same, see below:

$$P_1 = (0, 403), P_2 = (60, 403), P_3 = (60, 458), P_4 = (280, 458), P_5 = (340, 298)$$

On the other hand, there is a big difference in the computational efficiency (time) between analytical and numerical methods. Having the identical number of population (20 individuals) the analytical approach requires about 5 minutes, whereas the numerical method more than 5 hours in order to reach the optimal solutions.

In our opinion to optimise the thermoforming process for flat composite structures it is much more convenient to use analytical simplified approaches under one condition that the analytical formulae used in the evaluation of the residual stresses is correct. On the other hand, it is possible to use also strict numerical method at the optimal stage of heating procedure to observe the differences between numerical and analytical formulations.

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